

NOVEL METHODS FOR IDENTIFICATION AND BIOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF ESSENTIAL OILS OBTAINED FROM SECONDARY METABOLITES

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ABSTRACT

Essential oils (EOs) are concentrated, volatile liquids that are extracted from various plant sections. Terpenes and terpenoids in particular have a variety of medicinal properties, including being anticancer, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antiallergic. The research that is now available suggests that EOs have antifungal which is thought to have a substantial potential application in the pharmaceutical sector. Therefore, the objective of this review is to give a summary of what is currently known about EOs for use in the pharmaceutical and medical industries.

Figure: 01

Reference:13

Table: 01

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Introduction

In recent decades, the concept of encouraging people to utilize organic products in their daily lives has gained traction all around the world. One of the most widely used natural items overall has been essential oils (EOs). Essential oils are highly concentrated hydrophobic liquids that come from different kinds of plants. They have categories according to their chemical and physical characteristics. Many research investigations have been carried out on the pharmacological properties of EOs, ranging from antibacterial¹. Several investigations have been conducted on the pharmacological effects of EOs, ranging from antifungal², antibacterial³, Antiviral, antihelminth, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, Insecticide, antinociceptive properties, immunomodulator.

Terpenes (pinene, myrcene, limonene, terpinene, and p-cymene) are described as compounds with simple hydrocarbon structures, whereas terpenoids (oxygen-containing hydrocarbons) are modified classes of terpenes with various functional groups and oxidized methyl groups moved or removed at various positions. According to research, terpenes may interfere with protein and DNA synthesis, cause cell rupture, and have antimicrobial effects on bacteria that are both sensitive to and resistant to antibiotics. Among the terpenes that showed antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* were carvacrol, carvone, eugenol, geraniol, and thymol.

Terpenoids were also shown to be one of the secondary metabolites produced by aromatic and medicinal plants that were essential in the development of disease resistance. In addition, monoterpenoids have an antibacterial property that disrupts the formation and proliferation of microbes as well as their physiological and metabolic processes. Drug resistance among bacteria and fungi is one of the main issues in public health. Due to their toxicity and adverse medication effects, treating fungal infections, particularly those caused by the *Trichophyton*, *Candida*, and *Aspergillus* species, is particularly difficult. Thymol and carvacrol, two phenolic chemotypes, were discovered in *T. pulegioides* in numerous European nations. The existence of the α -Terpinyl acetate (α -TA) chemotype in *T. pulegioides* hasn't,

however, been sufficiently studied. A. Michet and co-authors showed that the major component in the essential oils of *T. pulegioides* was α -TA. Effect of α -TA essential oil on the fungus under investigation Stronger than the control itraconazole, Aspergillus and Trichophyton had an even greater impact on these bacteria⁴.

Fig. 1: The potential benefits of terpenes and terpenoids exist in EOs.

This review is going to provide a summary of what is currently known with respect to the potential impact on human health of terpenes and terpenoids, the main bioactive component of EOs, and their industrial applications (Fig.1). As an outcome, there will be significant opportunities to develop more and better concepts and research directions that can support widespread medicinal uses of EOs' elements in daily life.

Bioactive compounds of essential oils

Essential oils may be derived from a variety of plant components, including bark, buds, flowers, fruits, leaves, peels, roots, seeds, twigs, and whole plants from a single botanical source. They are concentrated liquids containing complex combinations of aromatic hydrophobic oily volatile chemicals. EOs are products derived from vegetable raw materials by pressing or distillation procedures, according to International Organization for Standardization (ISO).

However, there are several recognized outliers, including pale yellow (yellow mandarin), blue (chamomile), orange (sweet orange), and green (bergamot). Essential oils often have a strong scent and are colorless, especially when they are new. With time, EOs may be easily oxidized by air, heat, or light exposure, resulting in the black hue. EOs must thus be kept in a cold, dry environment⁶. Terpenes, terpenoids, phenylpropanoids, and other compounds are the four structural subgroups of the chemical components of Eos.

Terpenes

The primary components of EOs are terpenes or isoprenoids, which have molecules with the ability to form cyclic structures thanks to the carbon backbones of 2-methylbuta-1,3-diene (isoprene units) (Hyldgaard et al. 2012). The structural variety of terpenes is mostly influenced by the quantity of

isoprene units. One isoprene unit (C₅), monoterpenes (C₁₀), sesquiterpenes (C₁₅), diterpenes (C₂₀), triterpenes (C₃₀), and tetraterpenes (C₄₀) combine to make hemiterpenes.

A small number of the terpenes included in EOs are hemiterpenes. The most notable HT is isoprene, which is released by many different plants and tree leaves, including those of conifers, oaks, poplars, and willows. Angelic, tiglic, isovaleric, and senecioic acids are a few hemiterpenes as examples. Sesquiterpenes are the next most common component of EOs, making up 90% of them (Falleh et al., 2020). Additionally, minute levels of diterpenes, triterpenes, and tetraterpenes and their oxygenated derivatives have been found.

Terpenoids

Another class of terpenes called terpenoids is made up of oxygen molecules that are created by metabolic changes. Terpenoids are classified as phenols, epoxides, alcohols, aldehydes, esters, ethers, and ketones. These bioactive substances provide many biological properties, including antifungal and antibacterial properties.

Techniques for terpene and terpenoids separation and purification

The methods for separating terpene and terpenoid compounds from plants as well as the approach for figuring out structure elucidation were demonstrated. The phase that takes the longest is pretreatment. The physical state of the sample—which might be liquid or solid—determines this step. A number of methods are used to reduce the solid sample's size, such as heating, steaming, and dry distillation. The sample is then ground into a powder. Another choice for liquid samples is to use chemical or solvent treatment. To increase the efficiency of the extraction process, sample preparation is crucial. Maceration, soxhlet extraction, solvent extraction, pressured liquid extraction, and hydrodistillation are examples of conventional terpene and terpenoids extraction techniques⁷.

Hexane, petroleum ether, and other solvent extraction techniques are used to separate mono and sesquiterpenoids. Chloroform and ether can also be used to extract diterpenes, sterols, triterpenoids, and lactones of less polar sesquiterpenes. The ethyl acetate and acetone extracts contain triterpenoids, steroids, and oxygenated diterpenoids. Ethanol, methanol, and water are used in the extraction of highly oxygenated, polar triterpenes as well as triterpenoid. The polar solvents acetone, aqueous methanol (80%), and ethanol were used for total extraction. The terpenoids were then extracted sequentially using hexane, chloroform, and ethyl acetate in a subsequent extraction process.

A complex variety of chemicals is produced during compound extraction. Purification techniques are increasingly used to isolate certain chemicals. Because terpene and terpenoids have different structures, different purification processes apply. These processes also depend on the target molecule's chemical properties, the quantity and quality of the starting plant material, and the accessibility of tools and reagents. The ideal extraction technique will be determined by the characteristics of a certain terpene. Subsequently, the procedures for compound identification, characterization, and authentication are as follows: Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS), Liquid Chromatograph (LC), High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC), Fast-GC Analysis, Liquid-Liquid Extraction (LLE), High-Performance Counter-Current Chromatography (HPCCC), and Ultra-High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC)⁸.

Terpenes and Terpenoids effects on human health

Many research conducted in the last few decades have shown how important terpenes and terpenoids are for maintaining human health. The greatest classes of organic chemicals generated in the essential oils of different plants are these bioactive compounds, which are composed of several isoprene units. Due to the action of monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, diterpenes, triterpenes, tetraterpenes, and glycoside compounds, it has been shown in numerous in vitro and in vivo studies to be effective as anti fungal, anticancer agents, antimicrobial, antiinflammatory, antioxidants, antiallergic, neuroprotective, antiaggregator, anticoagulation, sedative, and analgesic .

Terpenes and Terpenoids are a source of vitamins A, E, K, and coenzyme Q10, this molecule can be found in a number of human nutritional and health products. In most animals, including humans, even the carotenoid and tocopherol molecules in this category are vital sources of vitamins ⁹.

Antifungal

The impact of Terpenes and terpenoids essential oil on the studied fungus *Aspergillus* and *Trichophyton* was extremely potent, outperforming the control treatment of itraconazole on both microorganisms. Prior research has demonstrated a potent antifungal action of *Thymus tosevii* essential oil, even at low doses of 0.25–1.0 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$, where the quantity of α -TA was only 12.3%.

Our examination using the α -TA analytical standard validated that the potent antifungal properties of α -TA essential oil could be ascribed to the elevated levels of α -TA and perhaps, the existence of other bioactive chemical components like

The substantial antifungal action of α -TA essential oil was validated by our investigation using the α -TA analytical standard. This might be attributable to the large amount of α -TA and perhaps the presence of additional bioactive chemical constituents such α -terpineol, geraniol, and α -terpinene. In further investigations, the antimicrobial properties of geraniol and α -terpineol on other bacteria were also reported. It's important to note that, compared to fungi and dermatophytes, *Candida* yeasts exhibited a higher degree of resistance to α -TA essential oil in our investigations. However, they were marginally more sensitive to *C. parapsilosis* than to itraconazole.

The research's overall results confirmed the strong antibacterial properties of pure α -TA and *T. pulegioides* α -TA chemotype essential oil against human pathogenic pathogens. The antibacterial effects of pure α -TA and essential oil from *T. pulegioides* are explained (Table-1).

Based on the findings of all the microorganisms examined, the bacteria showed the least amount of growth inhibition when exposed to pure or essential α -TA. The MIC values that were found ranged from 31.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ to 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

Table -1: *Thymus pulegioides* essential oil α -terpinyl acetate chemotype minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) and minimum fungicidal concentrations (MBCs/MFCs) values, as well as the analytical standard of α -terpinyl acetate against several microorganism groups (SD—standard deviation)

Microorganisms	α -Terpinyl Acetate		<i>T. pulegioides</i> α -Terpinyl Acetate Chemotype Essential Oil		Antifungals
	MIC	MBC/MFC	MIC	MBC/MFC	MIC
	Mean \pm SD, $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$				

<i>Escherichia coli</i>	125.00 ± 0.50	125.00 ± 0.50	31.30 ± 0.10	31.30 ± 0.10	0.50 ± 0.00 ^a
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> SC 6359	1.60 ± 0.20	6.30 ± 0.10	0.40 ± 0.00	6.30 ± 0.20	3.00 ± 0.00 ^c
<i>Candida parapsilosis</i> CBS 8836	2.00 ± 0.10	125.00 ± 1.00	8.00 ± 0.10	125.00 ± 1.00	32.00 ± 0.00 ^c
<i>Candida albicans</i> CBS 2730	8.00 ± 0.20	31.30 ± 0.10	31.30 ± 0.10 8.00 ± 0.15	31.30 ± 0.10	0.25 ± 0.00 ^c
<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> ATCC 9533	1.60 ± 0.20	25.00 ± 1.00	0.02 ± 0.00	6.30 ± 0.20	32.00 ± 0.00 ^c

Anticancer

Cancer is a regenerative illness that affects aberrant and uncontrollably growing cells in any region of the body. It may interfere with the regular operation of its host cells' homeostasis by assault or dissemination to different areas of the body. It is one of the main causes of morbidity and mortality in the modern world, accounting for 30% of all adult premature deaths (30–69 years old), ranking second globally behind cardiovascular disease and one in six human fatalities. It is also anticipated that the number of cancer-related fatalities would keep rising. The daily routines of living that are carried out are influenced by internal, external, and incapacity variables, which results in this cancer. A diet rich in foods can shield the body from variables that increase the risk of cancer¹⁰.

The greatest classes of chemical molecules found in the essential oils of different plants are terpenes and terpenoids, which are important in preventing cancerous growths¹¹.

Anti-inflammatory

Recent research has demonstrated the physiological significance of terpenes and terpenoids in reducing inflammatory symptoms, most likely by blocking many pathogenic stages in the inflammatory process. The host's defensive reaction to foreign objects, which are often caused by microbial infection and/or tissue injury, is inflammation. Acute and chronic inflammatory illnesses that result in significant or protracted tissue damage can be caused by dysregulation of inflammatory responses.

Rat models with adrenalectomy were used to assess myrcene's potential anti-inflammatory effects in the treatment of renal inflammation. The mechanisms were proposed to be linked to the upregulation of endogenous antioxidants like catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutases (SODs), and glutathione (GSH) and the downregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α) and anti-inflammatory markers (IL-4 and IL-10). Rat models with adrenalectomy were used to assess myrcene's potential anti-inflammatory effects in the treatment of renal inflammation. The mechanisms were proposed to be linked to the upregulation of endogenous antioxidants like catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutases (SODs), and glutathione (GSH) and the downregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α) and anti-inflammatory markers (IL-4 and IL-10)¹².

Anti-allergic

Inflammation with T cell and granulocyte (eosinophil, neutrophil, and mast cell) infiltration characterizes allergic disorders. Mast cells are important in practically all allergy disorders, usually at the allergic disease's last stage¹³.

The production of inflammatory cytokines, including IL-4, IL-5, IL-13, and IL-1 α/β , is initiated by mast cells through the synthesis of prostanoids and proinflammatory leukotrienes. This process also stimulates the activation of other cells, including neutrophils, monocytes, basophils, eosinophils, and lymphocytes. These anti-allergic substances come from a variety of sources, including microbes, plants, and animals. Their diverse modes of action include attaching to the epitope found in allergens, altering the gut microbiota and intestinal epithelial cells, modifying the presentation of antigens and T cell differentiation, and preventing effector cell degranulation. The production of inflammatory cytokines, including IL-4, IL-5, IL-13, and IL-1 α/β , is initiated by mast cells through the synthesis of prostanoids and proinflammatory leukotrienes. This process also stimulates the activation of other cells, including neutrophils, monocytes, basophils, eosinophils, and lymphocytes. Anti-allergic substances originating from microorganisms, plants, and animals that work through a variety of mechanisms, including adhering to the epitope found in allergens, modifying the T cell's differentiation and antigen presentation, and preventing the degranulation of effector cells.

The anti-allergic properties of many terpenes and terpenoids have been investigated. One of the sesquiterpene constituents of *Atractylodes japonica*, Atr, has the ability to suppress the degranulation of rat peritoneal mast cells (RPMC), the release of tryptase and histamine, and intracellular calcium levels. Moreover, decreased histidine decarboxylase expression and activity in activated HMC-1 cells were caused by decreased tryptase and histamine release from PMA plus A23187-stimulated HMC-1 cells. In the serum of PCA-induced mice, atr lowered the levels of histamine, IgE, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, vascular endothelial growth factor, and IL-13. ATR has efficacy in treating mast cell-mediated allergic responses.

Antioxidant

Certain EOs are frequently utilized to prevent a number of chronic illnesses and have a significant role in lowering oxidative stress. *Matricaria chamomilla* EOs include a bicyclic sesquiterpene derivative called chamazulene, which has the ability to balance the amount of reactive oxygen species (ROS) on bovine aortic endothelial cells-1 (BAECs), which rises when H₂O₂ and high glucose are administered. *Entada abyssinica* is the source of ursolic acid, a pentacyclic triterpenoid carboxylic acid. Using the FRAP, DPPH, and ABTS methods, ursolic acid's antioxidant activity was shown to be 1.43 ± 0.080 , 2.87 ± 1.19 , and 7.04 ± 1.29 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively.

Various aromas in wine are caused by certain terpeneoids, such as α -pinene, limonene, nerol, terpinol, geraniol, linalool, and myrcene. With an IC₅₀ of 12.57 ± 0.18 mg/ml, α -pinene demonstrated the largest impact on radical scavenging, followed by limonene and nerol, at 13.35 ± 0.26 and 26.08 ± 2.28 mg/ml, respectively. This is consistent with the findings of the reducing power assay, which show that α -pinene has the highest reducing power of all the compounds (213.7 ± 5.27 mg/ml). \angle nerol (79.15 ± 3.75 mg/ml), limonene (133.48 ± 6.22 mg/ml), terpinol (73.92 ± 3.34 mg/ml), geraniol (73.78 ± 3.94 mg/ml), linalool (43.97 ± 1.09), and myrcene (21.59 ± 1.14 mg/ml) followed.

Applications of EO as natural food preservatives: potential and constraints

Essential oils may be utilized as a food preservative for a range of foods, including dairy products, meat, breads, cereals, fruits, and vegetables. Food items can degrade due to a variety of infections, such as *Salmonella spp.*, *Clostridium spp.*, *E. Coli*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *S. cerevisiae*,

Penicillium expansum, and *Listeria monocytogenes*. Of them, *L. monocytogenes* has been identified as the primary cause of both human and animal severe illnesses .

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